

STOCHASTIC APPROACH TO MICROMECHANICAL MODELING OF POROUS SOLIDS

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Abstract

We use statistical modeling to predict the overall elastic moduli of linearly elastic solids with multiple pores of various shapes. The model is based on the evaluation of contributions from the pore subset selected using the design of experiments approach. It is shown that the accuracy of the model predictions depends on the choice of pore geometry parameters as model factors. The model is validated by comparing the results with direct finite element simulations and predictions obtained by the ellipsoidal approximation of pores.

1 Introduction

In this paper we present an approach to characterization and statistical modeling of contribution of irregularly shaped pores to the overall elastic properties of porous materials. We illustrate our approach by considering a sample of the carbon/carbon composite (C/C) manufactured by chemical vapor infiltration of carbon fiber preform. This manufacturing process results in a porous material (typical porosities are in the 2-15% range) with pores having highly irregular shapes, as illustrated in Fig. 1. These shapes are influenced by the local arrangement of fibers, the infiltration parameters and carbon deposition rates. Characterization and modeling of C/C material constituents including carbon fiber bundles [1,2], pyrolytic carbon [3,4] and pores approximated by ellipsoids [5,6] are discussed elsewhere.

Fig. 1. Examples of irregularly shaped pores present in carbon/carbon composite material

The objective of this paper is to characterize distribution of irregular pores in the material and develop a statistical micromechanical model to predict the overall stiffness based on the proper choice of morphological parameters reflecting pore shapes and orientations. Note that the spatial distribution effects, e.g. clustering of pores, are not included in the scope of this paper as they were not observed in the considered specimen; the spatial distribution of the voids is assumed to be uniform.

Our studies are based on the X-ray microtomography (μ CT) information obtained as described in [7]. Microtomography is routinely utilized in micromechanical modeling to characterize microstructure of heterogeneous materials. The obtained data is usually either directly used to develop a finite element mesh reproducing the scanned microstructure as in [8] or processed to determine a typical ellipsoidal inhomogeneity and utilize it in a certain homogenization procedure as in [9].

A possible of dealing with irregularly shaped pores involves combination of analytical micromechanical modeling with numerical approaches to evaluate contributions of individual pores to the effective elastic properties, see [10], [11]. In particular, in [11] the finite element analysis (FEA) was utilized to find contributions of several pore shapes typical for carbon-carbon composites. However, performing FEA simulations for every individual pore in a typical specimen of interest may be prohibitively time consuming due to the large numbers of pores: the sample analyzed in this paper contained around 10,000 individual voids in 1 cm³. Thus, one of the main reasons for considering statistical approaches is the ability to construct prediction models based on such characteristics of pore shapes that can be obtained without the FEA simulations. Another reason is to determine the pore geometric parameters

that are of the most significance for the overall mechanical response of the considered composite.

The microstructure of the C/C considered in this paper was characterized by X-ray computed microtomography performed at the Institute of Materials Science and Engineering I, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany. The scanned cubic specimen was cut to the size of 1x1x1 cm³ from the CVI infiltrated C/C laminate consisting of four 2.2 mm unidirectional C/C layers ([0°/90°]₂), separated by 0.4 mm layers of chemical vapor infiltrated random felt. The μ CT procedure utilized for characterization of this specimen has been previously reported in [7].

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes how the parameters defining contribution of an irregular pore to effective elastic properties are determined. Section 3 outlines our approach to statistical modeling using design of experiments methods. Sections 4 and 5 present the development of three- and four factor pore compliance contribution statistical models respectively. Validation of the proposed four factor statistical model is given in Section 6. Section 7 provides conclusions and potential directions for future investigations.

2 Contributions of Individual Pore Shapes

The evaluation of contribution of individual pores to the effective material properties is based on the pore compliance contribution tensor called \mathbf{H} -tensor [12]. The fourth rank compliance contribution tensor \mathbf{H} is defined as a set of proportionality coefficients between remotely applied homogeneous stress field $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0$ and the additional strain $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ generated in the material due to the presence of a cavity:

$$\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{H} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 \quad (1)$$

where “:” denotes the contraction over two indices. The choice of micromechanical model used to predict the effective elastic properties of a material with many pores depends on their concentration. If pores are sufficiently away from each other (dilute limit), the non-interaction approximation can be used. In this case, we calculate the overall compliance contribution tensor by direct summation:

$$\mathbf{H}_{RVE}^{NI} = \sum_i \mathbf{H}_{(i)} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{(i)}$ is the compliance contribution tensor of an individual pore and the summation is performed over all defects present in the representative volume element (RVE). Denoting by \mathbf{S}_0 the compliance tensor of a matrix material, we obtain the following expression for the effective compliance tensor:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S}_0 + \mathbf{H}_{RVE}^{NI} \quad (3)$$

from which all effective elastic parameters of the porous material can be extracted.

For non-dilute distribution of pores, more advanced micromechanical schemes are often used. For example, predictions for the overall elastic compliance of pores by the Mori-Tanaka method [13,14] in terms of \mathbf{H}_{RVE}^{NI} is given by a simple formula [12]:

$$\mathbf{H}_{RVE}^{MT} = \mathbf{H}_{RVE}^{NI} / (1 - p) \quad (4)$$

where p is the volume fraction of pores.

In the presentation below, we assume pores to be inserted in the homogenized isotropic material with Young’s modulus E_0 , bulk modulus K_0 , and shear modulus G_0 . A mixture of carbon fibers and PyC matrix in actual C/C composites is neither homogeneous nor isotropic, especially, for non-random fiber distributions. However, we utilize this assumption to emphasize contributions of various pore shapes without significant complication of the stochastic models. The more accurate approach would involve simultaneous multiscale modeling for various inhomogeneity types which is beyond the scope of this paper.

To evaluate contributions of individual pore shapes to the effective material properties, we introduce the dimensionless parameters: \tilde{E}_1 , \tilde{E}_2 , \tilde{E}_3 , \tilde{K} , \tilde{G} . These five parameters are related to the effective (non-interaction approximation) material properties as follows:

$$\frac{E_i}{E_0} = \frac{1}{1 + p\tilde{E}_i}, \quad \frac{K}{K_0} = \frac{1}{1 + p\tilde{K}}, \quad \frac{G}{G_0} = \frac{1}{1 + p\tilde{G}} \quad (5)$$

Three parameters \tilde{E}_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) characterize changes in the Young’s modulus in x_i -direction, which are induced by the pores of the same shape in the case when these pores are parallel to each other.

Parameters \tilde{K} and \tilde{G} represent change in bulk and shear moduli produced by the pores of the same shape in case when these pores are randomly oriented. All five parameters can be expressed in terms of the \mathbf{H} -tensor components as shown (no summation over repeating indices):

$$\tilde{E}_i = \frac{E_0}{p} H_{iii}, \quad \tilde{K} = \frac{T_{ijj}}{3}, \quad \tilde{G} = \frac{3T_{ijj} - T_{ijj}}{15} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{T} is the Wu's strain concentration tensor, related to \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{S}_0 as $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{T} : \mathbf{S}_0$ [15].

In the case of regular pore shapes, the elasticity problem for a single pore can be solved analytically and explicit expressions for \mathbf{H} -tensor can be found. For the irregular pore shapes observed in C/C, the compliance contribution tensors can be calculated by FEA as follows. The individual pore meshes are placed in a reference volume large enough to exclude influence of external boundary conditions on the strain state around the pore. The setup is meshed with 3D linear tetrahedral elements and subjected to 6 loadcases for every pore shape. The mechanical responses calculated from the corresponding FEA simulations are processed in MATLAB to determine the components of pore compliance contribution tensors. For detailed discussion of the procedure to calculate \mathbf{H} -tensors of irregularly shaped pores see [11].

3 Design of experiments approach

Micromechanical modeling procedure described in the previous section provides an approach to evaluating contribution of pores to the overall elastic response utilizing FEA simulations for each pore shape. However, using this approach to model real-world material systems which may contain a large number of irregularly-shaped pores with high variability in geometric parameters and orientation is infeasible due to very high computational costs. A possible approach to account for variation of pore geometries is to develop a stochastic model, which takes pore geometric parameters as input variables and provides pore compliance contribution (PCC) parameters as an output.

One of the ways to develop such a model is to perform FEA simulations on a set of irregular pores with various geometries. Then, using statistical methods such as linear or non-linear regression, the

obtained data can be processed to construct an empirical formula (usually a multivariate polynomial) that relates the input variables (pore geometry parameters) to the pore's contribution to effective elastic properties. For the model to be accurate, a very large dataset is usually required to get good estimates (narrow confidence intervals) of the model coefficients and predictions.

To minimize the number of simulations required for construction of a statistical model, the design of experiments (DoE) approach is usually applied. A special software tool (such as MATLAB, SAS, JMP, etc.) is used to select the most efficient set of design points (combinations of input parameters) from the full design space (total number of possible combinations, or, in our case, total set of all pores), such that a good prediction model can be obtained with the minimal number of simulations.

For the development of PCC model, the authors chose to construct and run the I-optimal design using DoE module in JMP software [16]. The optimization criterion for I-optimal designs is minimization of the integrated variance of the model predictions over the entire design space. In other words, the width of confidence intervals for predicted values should not vary significantly across the design space. It should be noted that the width of confidence intervals grows in the vicinity of the design space boundaries (extreme values of design parameters).

After calculating the PCC factors for pores corresponding to the selected design points, their values were processed utilizing the Response Surface Methodology [17,18] to develop the stochastic models of pore contributions to effective elastic moduli. The result is presented as a multivariate polynomial model. From the practical standpoint, there is always a trade-off when choosing between flexibility of the model (order of the polynomial), power of the model (confidence limits) and the number of experiments required for the analysis. The authors used a second-order model because of its ability to capture nonlinearities in the response with a feasible number of experiments to get high-quality predictions.

4 Three-factor model based on pore principal moments of inertia

Based on the previous studies [19,20], the following parameters were chosen as input for the

development of the PCC model of an isotropic matrix material with irregularly shaped pores: principal moments of inertia (PMIs) of the pore shapes (I_{11}, I_{22}, I_{33}) and Poisson's ratio of the matrix (ν). Since the values of PMIs are size-dependent, the ratios I_{11}/I_{33} and I_{22}/I_{33} were considered to separate contribution of pore shapes from their volumes. The range of values for the input parameters was established from statistical processing of the entire pore set from μ CT data, see [21] for details. The empirical distribution functions for each of the parameters (I_{11}/I_{33} and I_{22}/I_{33}) were analyzed and the range was chosen between the values corresponding to the 2.5% and 97.5% points of the curve. The range of values for the Poisson's ratio was chosen to be 0.0 – 0.4, which includes values for carbon/carbon composite materials, as well as other types of ceramics and metals. The ranges of the input variables are summarized in Table 1. It should be noted that within the chosen range of parameters I_{11}/I_{33} and I_{22}/I_{33} , some of the combinations of values are incompatible due to the properties of PMI. The values of PMI are limited by two constraints. The first constraint comes from the sorting of PMI according to $I_{33} > I_{22} > I_{11}$. The second constraint is defined as $I_{11}/I_{33} + I_{22}/I_{33} \geq 1$. This is an inherent property of the PMI as can be shown by the generalized perpendicular axes theorem [22].

An I-optimal design calculation was run in the DoE module of the JMP software with the ranges of model factors indicated above. The calculations resulted in a design table containing 53 combinations of input variables for each of the experimental runs. Using this table, geometries with the desired values of I_{11}/I_{33} and I_{22}/I_{33} were selected from the total dataset of pores obtained from μ CT data. Since the number of pores in the dataset is finite, it was impossible to find pores with parameters that exactly match the values of the input

parameters. Therefore, the pores with the smallest deviation from these values were chosen. Average differences between the actual and design parameters were -0.0008 and 0.0084 for I_{11}/I_{33} and I_{22}/I_{33} , respectively. Root mean square errors (*RMSE*) were found to be 0.0307 for I_{11}/I_{33} , and 0.0325 for I_{22}/I_{33} .

Once the experimental pore set was selected and pore surface meshes were extracted using the procedure described in [21], a self-written MATLAB script was employed to create FEA models for MSC Marc Mentat 2010 software (www.mscsoftware.com) and process the output files to determine pore compliance contribution parameters $\tilde{E}_1, \tilde{E}_2, \tilde{E}_3, \tilde{K}, \tilde{G}$. For details on the FEA and post-processing procedures see [11].

Results of FEA simulations for the 3-factor designed experiment were processed and entered into the JMP software for statistical analysis. The "Fit Model" module was used to fit a 2nd degree response surface model to the input data. The results of statistical analysis for PCC parameters \tilde{E}_1, \tilde{K} and \tilde{G} are presented in Fig. 3 as plots of actual vs. predicted values. In these plots, the straight line represents the perfect fit when the predicted values coincide with the actual values (**Actual = Predicted**). The two curves below and above straight line represent the 95% confidence intervals for the predicted values. After visual inspection, the outlier data point shown as an empty circle in the graph was removed and the model was rerun to improve the accuracy of predictions. Based on the R^2 and *RMSE* values, we conclude that the 3-factor model is a reasonably good fit for bulk and shear moduli; however, the regression's fit values for Young's moduli contribution parameters were found to be lower. See Table 2 for R^2 and *RMSE* values for all five PCC parameters.

In an effort to improve accuracy of the proposed PCC model, visual analysis of the actual vs. predicted plot was performed for each of the estimated responses. It was observed that in the midranges for responses $\tilde{E}_1, \tilde{E}_2, \tilde{E}_3$, there is a significant number of points which fall beyond the confidence intervals. These points correspond to pores with very similar predicted response, but different values of the actual response.

Table 1. The ranges of input variables

Input variable	Min value	Max value
I_{11}/I_{33}	0.10	0.70
I_{22}/I_{33}	0.67	0.98
ν_0	0.00	0.40
S_V	2.30	3.30

Table 2. Accuracy of model predictions of 3-factor and 4-factor models

Model response	3-factor model		4-factor model	
	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE
\tilde{E}_1	0.56	0.10	0.87	0.08
\tilde{E}_2	0.73	0.11	0.75	0.11
\tilde{E}_3	0.80	0.26	0.82	0.28
\tilde{K}	0.99	0.12	0.98	0.21
\tilde{G}	0.90	0.08	0.92	0.08

An example of two pores with virtually the same predicted response and input parameters I_{11}/I_{33} , I_{22}/I_{33} and ν is shown in Fig. 2. Pore “a” is indicated in Fig. 3 as an empty square, and pore “b” as an empty triangle. Comparing the shape features of these two pores, it appears that pore “b” has more surface features and looks less convex than pore “a”. One of the ways to account for this difference would be to introduce in the model a non-dimensional surface area to volume ratio $S_v = S^{1/2}/V^{1/3}$, which is analogous to the sphericity parameter defined by Wadell as $\pi^{1/3}(6V)^{2/3}/S$ [24]. The range of values for S_v parameter was chosen using the same approach as for moments of inertia. The empirical distribution function for S_v was analyzed and the range was chosen between the values corresponding to the 2.5% and 97.5% points of the curve (see Table 1).

Fig. 2. Two pores with virtually identical principal moments of inertia parameters, but noticeably different mechanical response

Fig. 3. Results of the 3-factor experiment. Actual vs. predicted plots for PCC parameters \tilde{E}_1 , \tilde{K} and \tilde{G}

5 Four-factor model incorporating S_V parameter

For the development of a PCC model incorporating the S_V factor, we constructed a new 4-factor experimental design using the DoE module of JMP with the model factor ranges presented in Table 1. The I-optimal design calculation resulted in a design table containing 150 combinations of geometric factors for each of the experimental runs. Similarly to the previous design, it was impossible to find pores with exactly matching parameters, and pores with the smallest deviations in parameters were selected. Average deviations of the design parameters were -0.0039 for I_{11}/I_{33} , 0.0071 for I_{22}/I_{33} and 0.0129 for S_V . The root mean square errors ($RMSE$) were calculated as 0.0516, 0.0619 and 0.1562 for I_{11}/I_{33} , I_{22}/I_{33} and S_V , respectively.

Once the experimental pore set was selected and pore surface meshes were extracted, FEA simulations were performed for all pores to calculate their respective PCC parameters and the results were imported into JMP software. Once again, the “Fit Model” module was used to fit a 2nd degree response surface model to the input data. The results of statistical analysis for PCC parameters \tilde{E}_1 , \tilde{E}_2 and \tilde{E}_3 are presented in Fig. 4 as plots of actual vs. predicted values. It can be seen that the overall fit of the 4-factor model is better than that of the 3-factor model. This is evidenced by the increased values of R^2 shown in Table 2. The scatter has not changed significantly (similar $RMSE$ values) for all model responses except \tilde{K} , for which an increased scatter was observed. Also, due to the larger number of experimental runs, the new model has narrower confidence intervals for predicted values of pore compliance contribution parameters. Goodness of fit (R^2 and $RMSE$ values) for both models is summarized in Table 2.

Fig. 4. Results of the 4-factor experiment. Actual vs predicted plots for PCC parameters \tilde{E}_1 , \tilde{E}_2 and \tilde{E}_3

6 Validation of the four-factor model

For validation of the proposed stochastic 4-factor PCC model, we compared the model estimates to the direct FEA simulations on a new set of 150 pores which were not used for the model construction. Pore geometries were selected from the original dataset containing all available pores. For this experiment, the design space was constructed using uniform distribution of the input variables within the boundaries given in Table 1. For all five responses, the model shows good prediction characterized by the low bias and moderate scatter (see Table 3). It can be observed that *RMSE* values for all responses are similar to those obtained for the original dataset. Low mean error (*ME*) and moderate *RMSE* values allow to conclude that the model is satisfactory for the new dataset.

Table 3. Accuracy of model predictions from the validation study

Error	\tilde{E}_1	\tilde{E}_2	\tilde{E}_3	\tilde{K}	\tilde{G}
ME	-0.06	-0.06	0.05	0.08	-0.02
RMSE	0.14	0.16	0.31	0.30	0.08

7 Conclusions

Stochastic model can be used to evaluate contribution of pores to the effective elastic properties based on their geometric parameters (e.g. ratios of their principal moments of inertia I_{11}/I_{33} and I_{22}/I_{33}) and matrix material parameter (e.g. Poisson's ratio ν).

The results of statistical analysis show that the overall fit of 3-factor model constructed based on I_{11}/I_{33} , I_{22}/I_{33} and ν can be improved by incorporating the fourth factor S_V . This is evidenced by the increased values of R^2 provided in Table 2. The scatter of the 4-factor model compared to the 3-factor one does not change significantly (similar *RMSE* values) for all model responses except \tilde{K} , for which an increased scatter is observed. Also, due to the larger number of experimental runs, the 4-factor model has narrower confidence intervals for predicted values of pore compliance contribution parameters.

The potential improvements to the model can be achieved by identifying other statistically significant factors, which characterize pore shapes and their spatial distribution.

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